

US Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS®) delivering benefits and the Global HF Radar and Glider Initiative

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Abstract—

The United States Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS®) is a user-driven, coordinated network of people, organizations, and technology that generate and disseminate continuous data about our coastal waters, Great Lakes, and oceans supported by strong research and development activities. IOOS® is our Eyes on our Oceans, Coasts and Great Lakes that enable the United States to track, predict, manage, and adapt to changes in our marine environment and deliver critical information to decision makers to improve safety, enhance our economy and protect our environment. IOOS focuses on the “I” or integration. Integration is defined providing rapid access to multi-disciplinary data from many sources and to provide data and information required to achieve multiple goals that historically have been the domain of separate agencies, offices, or programs. There are plenty of examples and efforts underway within US Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS®) that are moving us to a fully integrated system. The United States National Ocean Policy states that we should achieve “an America whose stewardship ensures that the ocean, our coasts, and the Great Lakes are healthy and resilient, safe and productive, and understood and treasured so as to promote the wellbeing, prosperity, and security of present and future generations.” For US IOOS to be a vital contributor to this goal we suggest a need to move beyond Integration and deliver benefits to society. Technologies must be incubated and rapidly inserted to keep the US IOOS system operating effectively and efficiently. Since oceans know no boundaries, US IOOS is also the United States’ contribution to the Global Ocean Observing System which is part of the ocean contribution to the Global Earth Observation Systems of Systems (GEOSS). US IOOS is supporting the Blue Planet Initiative under GEOSS.

Keywords—component; Integrated Ocean Observing System; Ocean Observing; Global Earth Observation System of Systems; Blue Planet

I. INTRODUCTION

The Integrated Ocean Observing System, or IOOS®, a national program led by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)— is strategically positioned to serve the nation and the broader international oceans, coastal and estuarine communities. IOOS was created about ten years ago to facilitate a coordinated local, regional, national and international network of ocean and coastal observations, modeling, data analysis and communications that is helping to

protect life and property, sustain economic vitality, safeguard ecosystems, and advance quality of life for all people living on or nearby the sea or Great Lakes. How this all can come together was tragically illustrated late last fall, when Hurricane Sandy came ashore in a broad swath of destruction. IOOS figured importantly in helping predict where one of the worst storms in recent history would go. IOOS partners’ buoys and gauges along the east coast generated hourly updates from wind, wave, visibility, water levels, and air and water temperatures; high-frequency radar provided ocean current data that contributed to coastal wave forecasts; and an unmanned scientific “glider” deployed off New Jersey reported water temperature information—all feeding into the United States National Hurricane Center.

II. FOCUS ON INTEGRATION

U.S. IOOS has embarked on the command and control approach to bring these numerous and varied organizations together in an integrated fashion and continues to leverage the potentials for federal, non-federal and international synergy with IOOS programs. This year IOOS advanced the following data management efforts.

A. Core Web Services

The infrastructure for our digital world today is the World Wide Web, which is also the infrastructure for Data Management and Communications (DMAC). This fundamental decision means U.S. IOOS is not building infrastructure. Instead, it is leveraging the web’s existing architecture and building the base layer for digital exchange on web services, not web sites. US IOOS completed the Sensor Observation Service (SOS) the templates for IOOS SOS Profile V1.0. Go to [IOOSTech](#) wiki for technical documentation. Beta versions of the software ([52North](#) and [ncSOS](#)) that include these templates will be done by late April 2013.

B. Registry and Catalog

A services registry and a catalog of assets are essential and complementary features for a successful DMAC subsystem. The registry provides a searchable list of on-line ocean observing web services, or storefronts, where consumers can browse or download data. The catalog is a discovery portal

that displays locations, operational status, and other information about the observing assets or instruments published through these same data services. As these functions emerge and mature, they will provide a seamless, authoritative access point for ocean observations, simplifying system monitoring and enabling powerful data integration for all types of users.

Preliminary versions of the U.S. IOOS registry and catalog are accessible through the U.S. IOOS website, where the number of registered data services is steadily increasing. Enhanced versions of both functions will be deployed in 2013. Implemented in tandem with the U.S. IOOS core services described above, the registry and catalog functions will significantly enhance existing information technologies that are already being broadly leveraged across U.S. IOOS, delivering data and products to an interdisciplinary set of users.

C. Quality Assurance of Real-Time Ocean Data

As part of the U.S. IOOS DMAC core services, the U.S. IOOS Program Office initiated a sustainable, community-based project to establish written authoritative procedures for the quality control of real-time ocean sensor data collected for U.S. IOOS. This project is entitled the Quality Assurance of Real-Time Ocean Data (QARTOD), and formalizes cumulative efforts from previous community efforts and meetings. All of the known QA/QC programs in existence today provide parts to the solution, but none consolidates them in one document. The result of this effort is to develop consistent practices that can become formal U.S. procedures for data from the RAs and the ocean observing community at large. The objective is a sustainable process that will:

- Establish authoritative QA/QC procedures for each of the 26 U.S. IOOS core variables as necessary, including detailed information about the sensors and procedures used to measure the variables
- Produce manuals for these QA/QC procedures
- Define baseline QA/QC procedures from the list of individual QA/QC procedures and guidelines developed that can be used for certification of Regional Coastal Ocean Observing System (RCOOS) data providers
- Facilitate QA/QC integration with GOOS and other international ocean observation efforts
- Engage the federal agencies and RAs that are part of, or contribute to, U.S. IOOS that will use the established QA/QC procedures
- Work efficiently, without duplication of effort, to facilitate the implementation of common QA/QC procedures amongst U.S. IOOS partners

The first manual, dissolved oxygen, was published in December 2012. U.S. IOOS will publish manuals on waves, currents, temperature, and salinity in 2013.

III. DELIVERING BENEFITS

U.S. IOOS is in motion every day supporting maritime safety, ecosystem services and efficient commerce. U.S. IOOS enables decision making and underpins scientific advances.

The U.S. IOOS (both federal and non-federal) coastal buoys form our surface and subsurface coastal observation capability. These networks support federal, state, and local agencies; decision makers; and marine based industries in making life-saving and operational decisions on a daily basis. For example, activity on the US IOOS - NERACOOS website routinely spikes daily at 4am as fisherman and others who depend on the sea check the buoys to ensure the safety of their crew and the sustainment of their livelihood.

Buoys from both NOAA National Data Buoy Center (NDBC) and U.S. IOOS Regional Associations (RAs) were critical to forecasting the impact of Hurricane Irene. NOAA used the buoys from U.S. IOOS RAs (CariCOOS, SECOORA, and NERACOOS) to track the Hurricane, and initialize and verify forecasts. John Cannon of the NOAA's National Weather Service (NWS) Weather Forecast Office (WFO) Gray, ME said, "Buoy 'A' and 'B' (NERACOOS) were our focus at the WFO Gray, Maine, for this storm due to their unique positioning along and just upstream the Seacoast of New Hampshire and Southwestern populated beaches in Maine to determine the extent for the potential of coastal flooding...splash-over and beach erosion in real-time with Irene. With south southeasterly winds...the buoy waves held below 20 feet as Irene approached due to the short fetch in the region as Cape Cod acted as a buffer. We have a very limited climatology of tropical systems creating winds from this direction so the real-time information was crucial for our needs. Short Term Forecasts (STFs) were lowered to account for the ongoing situation during Irene's approach. The observation of limited wave action was a critical benchmark which caused our office to (accurately) limit our forecast and warnings for coastal flooding to 'minor'. This indeed verified to be the case. Higher waves (over 20 feet) were anticipated and reported at Buoy 'E' and 'I' (NERACOOS) in the more exposed wave situation along the Mid-coast Region and our concern shifted to that area. The Maine Geological Survey visited Popham Beach after the storm and confirmed up to 10 feet of beach erosion in that area."

The Kaunalapa Harbor in Lana'i is the most exposed harbor in the State of Hawaii. In the past year, the Lanai Oil Company would return 2-3 barges per year to Honolulu still full of fuel because ocean conditions were too rough for the barge to safely enter the harbor. Each time a barge was returned to Honolulu, it cost about 22,000, a large expense to the small fuel operations and the people of Lana'i. Since the Lanna'i Oil Company authorized the fuel barges to enter the harbor 24 hours prior to arrival, knowing the expected surge conditions of the harbor for the barge's arrival was crucial. In response the US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) and PaCIOOS and the University of Hawaii deployed a wave buoy

just outside the harbor in 2007. With the deployment of the buoy, barge operators knew ahead of time when they could safely make the trip and the lanai oil company did not return a single barge from 2007-2012. The real-time wave information provided by the buoy was “extremely helpful in predicting the surge conditions within the harbor,” said Terry McBarnet, President of the Lanai Oil Company, in 2012 when discussing the value of the buoy. “By taking the swell forecast 24 hours before the barge will arrive and the comparing that information to what we see on the wave buoys, it helps us predict the surge conditions during the critical period when the barge will be pumping fuel into our storage tanks.”

In 2012, NOAA’s Center for Operational Oceanographic Products and Services’ (CO-OPS) Physical Oceanographic Real Time System (PORTS[®]) was instrumental in the transport of four giant container cranes by the Merchant Vessel Zhen Hua 13 under the Chesapeake Bay and Francis Scott Key Bridges en route to the Port of Baltimore. The cranes are the biggest of their kind in the maritime industry and are designed to handle the containers of larger vessels soon to arrive when the Panama Canal expansion is completed in 2014. CO-OPS provided bridge clearance and oceanographic data to assist the vessel in the final leg of its two-month journey from China. An air gap sensor on the Chesapeake Bay Bridge measured the distance from the bottom of the bridge to the surface of the water, providing an accurate clearance measurement to ensure safe passage for the cranes. CO-OPS’ hydrodynamic model provided a forecast of water levels, currents, winds, and other environmental parameters that were crucial to deciding when the vessel would travel to the port. Actual clearance from the bottom of the bridge to the top of the cranes was nearly 10 feet, more than twice the minimum clearance of four feet needed by the vessel.

The immense value of integrated observations is also demonstrated by the huge difference even small monitoring and observation efforts can make. An example is found in the Pacific Northwest, where oyster hatcheries on the verge of collapse just a few years ago are again major contributors to the \$111 million West Coast shellfish industry. U.S. IOOS - NANOOS and NOAA’s Ocean Acidification Program are helping to restore commercial hatcheries and support shellfish growing operations. Using real-time data both offshore and at water intakes, oyster hatcheries in the Pacific Northwest are again in good health. Real-time data from offshore buoys provide an early warning system for the shellfish industry, signaling the approach of cold, acidified seawater 1 to 2 days before it arrives in the coastal waters where sensitive larvae and young shellfish are cultivated. The data enable hatcheries and growing operations to schedule hatching, growing, and harvesting to maximize production by knowing when and where water quality is best for operations.

IV. SUPPORT OF BLUE PLANET – HF RADAR AND GLIDERS

U.S. IOOS is supporting the Blue Planet Initiative under GEOSS. Two technologies are prime for global efforts.

A. High Frequency Radar (HF radar)

The U.S. has the largest HFR network – a total of 132 land-based radars – and the U.S. encourages international development of similar networks. The Group on Earth Observations (GEO) launched an effort to develop a Global HF radar network in 2012 to help integrate the roughly 300 HF radars deployed in 30 countries. Working with other nations will accelerate research in emerging uses for HFR, including data assimilation by models and ecosystem and climate research. The 2012 World Radio Communication Conference established an HFR frequency range so that HF radar can operate in its own radio frequency space free from interference from other types of HF band users.

Within the U.S., NOAA’s NWS has begun incorporating HF radar to validate currents and wave models for real-time purposes. NWS in the Eastern, Southern, Western, Pacific, and Alaska Regions have expressed interest in accessing HFR data. Specifically, the WFO in Miami, Florida is interested in comparing HF radar currents to outputs from a real-time ocean forecast system. HF radar data would benefit the National Ocean Service’s evaluation of real-time coastal and estuarine model results. In the future, HF radar data is planned to be used in near real-time to address wave/current interactions near harbor entrances and provide current observations for navigational purposes.

NOAA’s Weather Ready Nation Plan states that “improved marine forecasts of winds and waves create an economic benefit of \$95 million per year of commercial shipping from transit time savings and cargo loss reductions.” Improving depiction of surface currents in nearshore wave modeling systems is essential to the socio-economic vitality of our Nation. HFR data will strengthen impact-based decision support services for events that threaten lives and livelihoods, such as oil spill response, plume tracking, and water quality monitoring.

HF Radar also provided benefits during severe weather, illustrated as Hurricane Sandy raged forth in a broad swath of devastation and destruction last fall. HF radar worked in concert with the rest of the U.S. IOOS system before, during, and after the super storm. In addition to providing critical data to the 159 search and rescue responses last October, U.S. IOOS monitored developments by land and sea to figure importantly in helping predict where one of the worst storms in our Nation’s history would go. More than 40 land-based coastal HFRs provided ocean current data that contributed to wave and storm-surge forecasts.

Under GEO, blue planet the global HF radar task’s goals are:

- To make HF radar data available in a single standardized format in near real time
- To develop a Worldwide QA/QC standard
- To develop easy-to-use standard products
- To assure HF radar data assimilation in ocean and ecosystem modeling
- To develop emerging uses of HF radar in the areas of ecosystem, tsunami, and climate.

Australia, Korea and Spain are also operating HF Radar networks and have agreed under GEO to make their data available. US IOOS has agreed to host the global HF radar site, <http://www.ioos.noaa.gov/globalhfr/welcome.html>, where you can find links to the Australia, Korea and Spain. Under GEO three working groups have been formed to advance this effort:

- Data Management (Lisa Hazard, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, USA)
- Applications and Success Stories (Hugh Roarty, Rutgers University, USA)
- Best Practices in Deployment & Operation: Capacity Building (Lucy Wyatt, James Cook University, Australia)

B. U.S. Gliders

Over the past 5 years, U.S. glider operators have flown 25,722 days. Of those, 3,163 days were completed using IOOS funding and 17% of the glider days were funded by IOOS in coastal US waters. The remaining glider days were resourced with leveraging from several other federal, state, local agencies and private foundations. The resulting infrastructure provides a solid framework for a nationwide, operational, glider network; however, many of these assets were obtained via grants and contracts that do not provide ongoing funding for sustained operations and maintenance or data management. The US has a national glider plan (in draft) to maximize the benefit of existing investments by providing a mechanism for sustained operation and delivery of these subsurface profile data in a consistent manner to users around the country. The plan also identifies highest priority data gaps that must be filled to achieve a national subsurface sustained monitoring capability that can characterize the often-complex flows in coastal waters and meet the needs of diverse stakeholders in each region. A National Glider Asset Map was deployed by the U.S. IOOS program in 2012 and will include all historic and current glider flights once it is completed. The map includes data from glider missions since 2005 from several of the US IOOS Regional Associations (SCCOOS, NANOOS, CeNCOOS, MARACOOS) regional glider operations. The glider asset map can be viewed at: http://www.ioos.gov/observing/observing_assets/glider_asset_map.html.

The cost estimate to implement this plan, including operations and maintenance (O&M), acquisition and deployment of new gliders to fill priority data gaps, and acquisition of additional replacement gliders to minimize down time is provided. The

buildout of the network should include 7-10 gliders deployed at all times on lines along the east, west, and gulf coasts. This national network of 20-30 gliders can be maintained locally for about \$150K/year, with one glider in the water and one being refurbished at all times. Thus, operational costs will be \$3M-\$4.5M per year. With two gliders required for each line, and the cost of a new glider about \$150K, capital costs are \$6M-\$9M. Data management and operational data delivery would be the responsibility of IOOS.

Gliders are particularly effective for observing climate variability in the coastal ocean. The regional effects of large-scale climate variability, as by El Niño and the North Atlantic Oscillation, are of great societal importance. Such effects include changes in precipitation on land, and in commercially important species in the ocean. For example, sustained glider missions, supported by the NOAA Ocean Climate Observation Program and IOOS, have been observing physical and biological variables relevant to climate effects on the ecosystem of the California Current System [Davis *et al.*, 2008]ⁱ. These sustained observations [Todd *et al.*, 2011]ⁱⁱ have produced a simple index of climate variability based on temperature at 50 m depth. The glider observations are run along a few of the same lines as those occupied quarterly by the California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations. Thus the gliders augment the 60-year ongoing shipboard program, and support the goal of fisheries management. Gliders in particular offer a unique tool as they can be used for directed subsurface water column profiling in coastal environments that are not well sampled spatially and temporally with other systems.

U.S. IOOS - GCOOS partners at the University of South Florida College of Marine Science and Mote Marine Laboratory are coordinating glider missions to gain a better understanding of the dominant Gulf of Mexico red tide organism *Karenia brevis*. Gliders offer an effective means of three dimensional sampling for monitoring harmful algal blooms. The gliders are equipped either with a red tide detection system capable of identification of high concentration bloom conditions, or equipped a sensor suite including fluorometers, dissolved oxygen sensors, and passive acoustic recorders. The glider data helps to identify upwelling from the bottom Ekman layer. Such multidisciplinary collaborations utilizing gliders, traditional cell counts, satellite imagery, drifters, moorings and predictive circulation models are providing new insights to bloom evolution from onset to termination.

C. Global Gliders

Internationally, the potential use of gliders for ocean research was discussed at the OceanObs'99 conference in San Raphael, France, "... In terms of specific need, the Conference noted that gliders (self-steered profiling floats) offered a potential effective solution for repeated sampling through narrow, swift boundary currents. ..." and "... Technological advances help us improve cost-effectiveness, sampling, and distribution."

Ten years later, the use of glider technology was promoted during the OceanObs'09 conference in Venice, Italy. Testor et al. (2010) emphasized that gliders can help optimize the global ocean observing system. They also argued that combining glider deployments with ships, moorings, floats and satellites would enhance the capacity for observing the ocean by filling gaps left by the other observing systems. The OceanObs'09 Conference Statement noted, "There is potential for their [glider's] role in deep ocean observations and in taking observations under sea ice."

At the same conference, Meldrum et al. (2010) described key variables needed by the ocean and climate forecasting community that are challenging to measure, including biological variables, where current sensors rely on optical measurements that tend to experience bio-fouling problems. Glider technology may be able to resolve some of the issues involved in measuring essential ocean variables like sea surface salinity, pCO₂, pH, nutrients, and phytoplankton.

The Implementation Plan for the Global Observing System for Climate in Support of the UNFCCC (2010) states: "Promote and facilitate research and development (new improved technologies in particular), in support of the global ocean observing system for climate." Areas requiring research and technology development involve making improvements in ocean platforms, including increased capabilities for Argo floats, and improved glider and mooring technology.

Both Australia and Europe are developing glider fleets similar to the United States. The "Gliders for Research, Ocean Observation and Management" (GROOM), http://www.groom-fp7.eu/doku.php?id=public:about_groom, infrastructure design study will evaluate the requirements to set up a sustainable European glider infrastructure to safely operate individual as well as fleets of gliders in order to create a continuum of observations. Operations shall be coordinated to fill the gaps left by present marine observation systems on global, regional and coastal scale, with benefits for both fundamental marine research and operational oceanography. The objective for this design study for a European glider RI are to demonstrate that:

- a distributed architecture of "gliderports" around the European seas and overseas (see figure on the right), working in close coordination, is the required and cost effective way to operate fleets gliders in the combination with existing observing systems,
- this infrastructure is suitable to deploy, maintain and operate individual as well as fleets of gliders continuously for operational monitoring and research.
- such infrastructure can provide a world-class service to the research and environment monitoring communities.

Similarly in Australia, through the Integrated Ocean Observing System (IMOS) has set up the Australian National

Facility for Ocean Gliders (ANFOG). The Ocean Gliders facility operates a fleet of autonomous underwater ocean gliders that undertake measurements from shelf and boundary currents in Australian waters. Equipped with a variety of sensors, the gliders are designed to deliver ocean profile data. Furthermore, the unique design of the gliders enables them to move horizontally through the water while collecting vertical profiles. The use of these contemporary gliders provides a unique opportunity to effectively measure the boundary currents off Australia, which are the main link between open-ocean and coastal processes. The Ocean Gliders facility operates a number of gliders with target regions including the Coral Sea, East Australian Current off New South Wales and Tasmania, Southern Ocean southwest of Tasmania and the Leeuwin and Capes Currents off Western Australia. <http://imos.org.au/anfog.html>

The United States, Europe and Australia are committed to working with each other to ensure a global interoperable fleet of gliders.

V. SUMMARY

The more we develop US IOOS the more we understand that it is critical to work in a global environment. The ocean has no boundaries therefore neither should our observing systems. It has been great to see that this global sentiment is shared and working together is a common theme. Wanting to work together is half the battle. So working together, I am sure we that globally we will be able to become interdependent and indispensable.

VI. ACKNOWLEDEMENTS

Information for this paper was compiled from weekly and monthly reports, as well as powerpoint presentations developed by the US IOOS program office and across the eleven US IOOS Regions.

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